

Development and application of p-NIPAM barriers and repositories for microfluidic flow control. A proof of concept

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ABSTRACT

Passive fluid flow is not sufficient to meet new analytical requirements, therefore further research is needed in the field of flow control in order to improve the application of microfluidic systems. In this work, stimulus-sensitive materials have been studied to act as barriers and repositories to be integrated in μPADs. Poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (p-NIPAM) has been studied to act as a reservoir and flow retardant. As a reservoir, the swelling/de-swelling behaviour has been characterized as a function of temperature, kinetics, reservoir size and the influence of pH. As a flow retardant, a p-NIPAM ionogel was used to significantly slow down the flow and even stop it. This is very useful for preventing the mixing of reagents until a certain point in time or for controlling where the mixing occurs. The ionogel volume and the delay time were optimised. As proof of concept, they were used in a colorimetric μPAD for nitrite determination based on the Griess chemistry. The results demonstrate the feasibility of integrating the developed stimulus-sensitive materials in μPADs, enabling new applications where these tools are required.

1. Introduction

Microfluidics and the evolution observed in the technologies associated with its development have been key to the exponential growth observed in the area of miniaturized analytical devices, as they provide the necessary connectivity between the different elements of the classical analytical procedure. In the past two decades, there has been a significant growth in the use of capillary platforms that mainly use paper as support. These platforms are known as Paper-based Analytical Devices (μPAD). These devices enable a wide range of point-of-care applications; for instance, recent developments have demonstrated their critical importance in healthcare and clinical diagnostics [1–3], as well as in food safety [4,5] and processing through the detection of contaminants [6,7]. Furthermore, the field has expanded into cell biology and advanced drug screening [8,9], utilizing paper matrices to simulate complex biological environments [10], and environmental monitoring for the rapid detection of pollutants [11,12].

These platforms offer several advantages over other microfluidic

systems [1,13,14]. In terms of their strengths, the paper support allows the design of microfluidic structures capable of integrating different stages of the analytical process in a very economical way. These μPADs leverage the capillary action of paper to transport liquids without the need for external pumps or power sources [15]. This autonomous flow, combined with their low cost, portability, and ease of use, renders μPADs of great interest for the rapid and reliable detection of analytes in resource-limited settings [16]. Also, the chemical structure of these materials is easily modified, allowing their functionalization with a range of biomolecules through a covalent bond, charge-charge, and van der Waals interactions [14,17]. Besides, these structures do not require instrumental support, as they are compatible with ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) signal processing using tools such as smartphones [7,18,19]. Additionally, μPADs are environmentally friendly due to the biodegradable nature of the paper substrate and can be easily disposed of by incineration [6].

For the design of μPADs, it is necessary to understand both the fluidic characteristics of the material from which they are made and the flow

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control mechanisms. The latter will enable operations such as flow mixing, interrupting them to allow chemical reactions or separations, dissolving and transporting encapsulated reagents, and sequential injections or dilutions, among others. The capillary flow velocity can be controlled by altering the length, height, porosity, pore radius of the paper channel and fluid viscosity [20,21].

The different strategies applied for fluidic control on μ PAD can be classified into three main types. First, geometry-based methods rely on the alteration of the fluid channel architecture [22,23]. In contrast, mechanical methods involve the physical movement of components that enable connection, disconnection, or close proximity to the channel surface, though they often require user intervention [24,25]. At last, chemical and electrochemical methods offer more dynamic approaches; while some utilize substances embedded in the channel to cause variations in flow rates [12], others employ active mechanisms such as electrowetting, electrostatic control, or electroosmosis pumping to drive the fluid [21,26]. Each approach has its own advantages and disadvantages, including fabrication complexity, automation, functionality, and cost, as detailed in Table 1.

Despite these advances, a core scientific challenge remains: the lack of versatile materials capable of providing autonomous, multi-step fluidic control without relying on complex fabrication or external power sources. In practice, purely passive capillary flow is often insufficient for emerging analytical requirements, such as sequential reagent delivery or precise incubation times, as it is highly susceptible to environmental variables and sample viscosity [21,27]. Most current strategies are limited to a single function (either stopping flow or storing reagents), but rarely both, making it difficult to develop fully integrated, ‘sample-to-answer’ analytical procedures. To address these limitations, stimuli-responsive materials (SRM), also known as intelligent polymers, have emerged as a promising solution for flow regulation [28]. SRM respond to external stimuli changing their physical or chemical properties, enabling flow controls that were previously only possible in complex laboratory systems. These SRMs have been applied in various fields, such as controlled release of substances, drugs, sensitive coatings, shape memory materials, sensors, and biosensors. Most of these materials respond to stimuli such as temperature, light and pH, whereas others respond to less common stimuli such as magnetic fields, mechanical forces, or small molecules [29]. Many of its properties come from a transition in solubility or conformation of a macromolecule in the presence of a solvent under a stimulus effect. In this way, molecular-level transitions can be amplified because of a change in nanostructure or material properties [30].

In this context, the objective of this study is to overcome the aforementioned limitations by developing a μ PAD that integrates p-NIPAM for fast, low-cost, and ubiquitous analysis. To achieve this, we synthesize and characterize actuating polymers that respond to temperature, allowing the implementation of analytical operations such as flow control and reagent repository in solution.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials and reagents

The reagents used for the synthesis of hydrogels were N-

isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM), *N,N'*-methylenebis(acrylamide) (BIS), dextran, *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED) and ammonium sulfate (APS). For the nitrite determination, a N-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine 0.1% solution (NNED), a solution of sulfanilic acid 1% in 5% phosphoric acid (AS) and a nitrite standard solution were used. Solutions were prepared using purified water (Type III) obtained from a Milli RO12 Plus reverse osmosis unit coupled to a Milli Q PLUS 185 refining unit (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA). In the case of ionogels, the ionic liquid tetracyclotrihexylphosphonium dicyanamide (PDCA) was employed as solvent instead of Milli-Q water and 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid (DMPA) was added to the mixture as photoinitiator. All the reagents were of analytical grade and were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). All solutions were deposited on Whatman1 paper (Whatman, UK). Whatman qualitative filter paper grade 1 and double-sided adhesive tape from Plus Office S.L. (Ciudad Real, Spain) were used to fabricate the μ PAD.

2.2. Equipment, instruments and software

A Mini-Protean Tetra Cell Casting (Bio-Rad Laboratories, USA) was used for the polymerization of hydrogels as squared layers of a reproducible thickness. The thickness of the sheets was controlled with spacers. To initiate the photopolymerization of ionogels, a UV lamp model VL-6.MC from Vilber Lourmat (Marne La Vallée, France) was used. Paper pieces were cut using a Laser printer Rayjet 50 from Trotec (Marchtrenk, Austria). Images were captured using a compact camera Sony Hx400V with 50 \times optical zoom and 20.4-megapixel Exmor R CMOS sensor (Tokio, Japan). The optimised settings used to photograph were incandescent white balance, ISO 80, no flash, standard colour mode and fixed image size of 16:3 (3 M). Photographs were obtained in a homemade LED light box for uniform illumination. The hue or H component from the hue, saturation, value (HSV) colour space of the region of interest (ROI) of the membranes was determined. Image J software (Version 1.48, Wayne Rasband, National Institutes of Health, USA) was used along with the Colour Space Converter plugin to generate the mode values of the H parameter from the pixels (15.720) that compose the ROI. The ROI is defined as the area of the digitalised membrane selected to perform the colorimetric analysis in order to obtain analytical information. The H coordinate was selected because it directly correlates with the spectral shift of the chemical reaction, providing a more stable analytical signal against variations in ambient light compared to traditional RGB intensity [31].

Phase transition of the p-NIPAM was achieved using a heater with a 22 Ω resistance and 0.5 \times 0.5 cm dimensions fabricated on a printed circuit board and an 8 1/2-bit Digital Multimeter from Agilent Technologies (USA). Differences in weight between swollen and dry hydrogel were determined using an analytical balance DV215CD from Ohaus (New Jersey, USA) with 0.1 mg precision. All temperatures were precisely monitored and controlled using a non-contact infrared thermometer from Fluke (Washington, USA).

2.3. Synthesis of p-NIPAM layers

A layer of 8.0 \times 8.0 cm was synthesized as follows: 640 mg of NIPAM, 16 mg of BIS, and 80 mg of dextran were weighed and dissolved

Table 1
Comparative analysis of flow control strategies in μ PADs.

Strategy	Mechanism	Complexity	Cost	Limitations	Ref
Geometric	Lamination and laser ablation	Moderate	Low	Static control	[22]
Geometric	Channel Patterning	Low	Low	Limited to mixing	[23]
Mechanical	Modular 3D printing	High	Moderate	Requires specialized 3D printing equipment.	[24]
Mechanical	Two-way magnetics valves	Moderate	Moderate	Requires external magnetic field/actuators.	[25]
Chemical	Electroosmotic pumping	High	High	Needs external power and electrodes	[26]
Chemical	Hydrophilic Channel	Low	Low	No dynamic control	[12]

in 4 mL of Milli-Q water. Later, 48 μL of TEMED and 200 μL of an APS solution 65 mM were added. The mixture was vigorously stirred (2000 rpm) and poured into a Bio-Rad mould with 0.75 mm spacers. The polymerization was carried out for 60 min at room temperature. The layer was then kept in a vessel with purified water.

2.4. Synthesis of p-NIPAM-ionogels

The p-NIPAM-ionogels were synthesized following the procedure developed by Benito-López et al. [32]. A pre-polymerization mixture solution was prepared by dissolving 14.5 mg of BIS, 456 mg of NIPAM, and 16.3 mg of DMPA in 1 mL of PDCA and stirring for 30 min at 80 °C in darkness. These mixtures were stored in the refrigerator until use.

To include the p-NIPAM-ionogels in the μPAD it was necessary to place known volumes of the mixture in the selected area and immediately apply 365 nm UV radiation for 10 min at a distance of 7 cm. During this process, the colourless liquids turned yellow, indicating that the polymerization of the p-NIPAM-ionogel was achieved. Once the polymerization was complete, the μPADs with the p-NIPAM-ionogel were washed first using Milli-Q water and then using ethanol to remove any excess of unpolymerised reactants.

2.5. Preparation of the μPAD , measurements conditions and data analysis

All the μPADs tested were laser cut using a laser printer. The printer parameters were adjusted to cut the paper without burning it, with a power of 66% at a speed of 5%. The papers were washed twice with a 1:1 water:ethanol mixture and vortexed for 5 min each time to remove the ash generated by the cut. Once dried, the desired volume of the ionogel mixture was deposited with the pipette and then irradiated.

For the incorporation of the p-NIPAM repository, a piece of p-NIPAM layer was cut into square pieces by punching and storing in Milli-Q water. The p-NIPAM was collapsed by heating at 45 °C for 30 s using a heater. The precise arrangement of the heater relative to the device is shown in the photograph provided in Fig. S11. Once it was dry, it was immersed in a 25 mL vial filled with the required solution at 25 °C for 2 h and before each weighing, excess surface water was carefully removed to ensure that only the absorbed water was measured. All measurements were carried out in triplicate.

p-NIPAM absorption capacity was calculated by weight differences between dry and swollen conditions or even other intermediate states. The pieces of hydrogel were weighted using an analytical balance. The filled weight values were normalized with respect to the weight of the collapsed p-NIPAM (dry weight) to avoid the variability of the cut based on the parameter described by Abdel-Mosen et al. [33] (Eq. 1).

$$\text{Swelling ratio (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Filled weight} - \text{Dry weight}) * 100}{\text{Dry weight}} \quad (1)$$

2.6. Structural analysis

The structural characterization of p-NIPAM deswelled, water, p-NIPAM-water, AS and p-NIPAM-AS was performed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR). The spectra of the starting materials and lyophilized gels were recorded using a Jasco FT-IR 4100 spectrometer (Jasco Inc., Easton, PA, USA) equipped with a ZnSe crystal for direct acquisition of Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) spectra. Measurements were recorded over a spectral range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the p-NIPAM repository

Several studies were conducted to characterize the p-NIPAM layers under different conditions.

p-NIPAM layers of three different thicknesses (0.75, 1.0 and 1.5 mm) were cut into rectangles of sizes 4, 6, 9, 16, 25, 30, 36, 49, 64, 81 and 100 mm^2 , and the absorption capacity of water at 25 °C was calculated, after an immersion period of 2 h. The results obtained can be observed in Fig. S12. For the same area, the fluid storage capacity of p-NIPAM scales linearly with thickness. Consequently, while the absolute volume increases proportionally to the sample thickness, the swelling ratio remains constant as it is an intrinsic property of the polymer network. However, as the thickness increased, a variation in the physical properties of the p-NIPAM was also found, becoming softer and more difficult to handle with respect to the 0.75 thickness. In addition, greater thickness requires higher heating power of the heating system per unit area.

The impact of repeated swelling-deswelling cycles on the absorption performance of p-NIPAM was also investigated. For this purpose, p-NIPAM squares of 0.75 mm thickness were subjected to several swelling/deswelling cycles, using a swelling time of 24 h in water at 25 °C. It was found that p-NIPAM always returns to the same dry weight, showing that it did not degrade in the heating processes and that the swelling ratio remains around 650% (Fig. 1) and can oscillate depending on the time left swelling.

The swelling kinetics allows us to determine the time required for a piece of hydrogel to reach a point where no more solvent can be loaded. To study this, three pieces of p-NIPAM hydrogel were swelled with Milli-Q water at 25 °C during increasing times (13, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 150 min) and weighed. At first, there is a high absorption that increases linearly with time but it seems to stop after 120 min, indicating that the equilibrium has been reached (Fig. S13).

All temperature-responsive polymers have a critical temperature, which can be either the upper critical solution temperature (UCST) or the lower critical solution temperature (LCST). p-NIPAM is a LCST-type polymer, and when the temperature is higher than the LCST, the p-NIPAM collapses, releasing the solution embedded in its structure.

The thermal behaviour below the LCST was investigated by immersing p-NIPAM samples of uniform size in vials containing 25 mL of distilled water at four different temperatures: 5, 10, 20, and 25 °C. After 2 h, the swelling ratio was calculated, revealing a clear temperature-dependent trend. As expected for this thermo-responsive polymer, it was found that these values were significantly higher for the p-NIPAM pieces that were at a lower temperature of 935% at 5 °C and 861% at 10 °C versus 733% at 20 °C and 650% at 25 °C (Fig. S14).

In contrast to polymers that collapse fully upon pH variations [34], p-NIPAM exhibits incomplete deswelling. Furthermore, this process is not completely independent of the pH environment. For study this purpose, phosphate buffers of 0.1 M concentration at pHs values ranged from 3.0 to 12.0 were used. The p-NIPAM samples were immersed at 25 °C and weighed before and after a 2-h swelling period (Fig. S15). A pH-

Fig. 1. p-NIPAM behaviour after several cycles of water swelling/deswelling. Data are presented as the mean of three independent replicates and error bars represent the standard deviation.

dependent swelling behaviour was observed, characterized by a reduction in buffer uptake at higher pH levels. This decrease followed a nearly linear trend until pH 9.0, beyond which a slight increase in absorption occurred. This agrees with previous studies, which showed that the polymer has difficulties retaining concentrated solutions of strong bases, such as NaOH [35].

To determine whether the swollen hydrogel suffers loss of the absorbed solvent due to evaporation and therefore the time that may elapse between the preparation of the swollen p-NIPAM and its use, the following test was performed. Six p-NIPAM pieces were used, half of which were swelled using Milli-Q water and the other half using ethanol. They were left to dry at room conditions (25 °C) for 2 h, and their weight was checked every 15 min (Fig. S16). In the case of water, evaporation occurs slower than with ethanol, and after approximately 80 min, 50% of the swollen water was lost (20 min in the case of ethanol). At 120 min, 30% of the water was still retained.

The hydrogel pieces were 2 h immersed in ethanol and methanol at 25 °C. The weight increase was found to be less than that observed when immersed in water and very similar for ethanol (515%) and methanol (493%), demonstrating that p-NIPAM hydrogel can also function as a repository for short tail alcohols (Fig. S17).

3.1.1. Structural analysis

ATR-FT-IR analysis was conducted for the structural characterization of the starting materials and the polymer, in order to confirm the successful swelling of water at 25 °C (Fig. 2A). The vibrational spectrum of the p-NIPAM deswelled reveals characteristic bands of 3295, 1654, 1542, 1387, and 1171 cm^{-1} (Table S11) [36]. The vibrational spectrum

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of A) p-NIPAM swelled (black) and p-NIPAM deswelled (red). B) AS (orange) and p-NIPAM swelled with AS (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of the p-NIPAM swelled reveals the same bands, adding a bands of 2100 cm^{-1} , due to the water retained [37].

3.2. P-NIPAM ionogels as flow barriers

The effectivity of the ionogel as a delayer was measured by placing a paper strip, which splits into two perpendicular arms of the same dimensions. Channel A contained ionogel, while channel B did not (Fig. 3). This μ PAD was supported in adhesive tape, and Bright Blue solutions were drop casted onto them. A digital camera was used to record the advance of the flow front and compare the times. The volumes of ionogel used for the experiment were 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 1.0 and 1.5 μL .

In all cases, the flow was delayed compared to the ionogel-free channel. The results reveal a clear transition in flow behaviour: for volumes between 0.5 and 0.8 μL , we observed a quantitative increase in delay times, whereas for volumes of 1.0 μL and above, the flow was completely stopped (Table S12), proving the utility of ionogels as barriers or flow delayers for future microfluidic sensors.

3.3. Proof of concept: Use of μ PAD for nitrite determination

Once the capability of p-NIPAM ionogels to slow down the flow and the ability of p-NIPAM hydrogels to release reagents were proven, the possibility of including these functionalities in a paper microfluidic device that could benefit from both capabilities was considered. The analysis of nitrites based on Griess chemistry was selected as a proof of concept. This reaction requires the mixture of two reagents that cannot be simultaneously added because it is a two-step reaction. First, the diazotization reaction between nitrous acid and AS occurs, followed by the azo coupling reaction of the diazonium salt with the NNED coupling agent, giving rise to a red-violet azo dye.

For the implementation of this chemistry in the microfluidic device, the 2 h filling of p-NIPAM with both reagents was first studied to determine which one would be more suitable for swelling. The results showed that in both cases, filling occurred in a similar way, increasing the p-NIPAM weight by 10 times the initial weight for NNED and 8 times for AS. Once it was observed that both could be used in the reservoir, they were tested in the μ PAD (Fig. 4).

The idea for the device was to retain one of the Griess reagents in the detection area (4), which is the meeting point of two different channels (A and B). One channel for the sample (B) deposited on zone (3) and the other for the p-NIPAM repository (1) filled with the second reagent of the Griess reaction for 2 h at room temperature. Therefore, tests were conducted when NNED was in the p-NIPAM reservoir and AS was retained in the detection zone and *vice versa*. The results showed that when NNED was placed in the detection zone and AS was retained by p-NIPAM, the μ PAD worked properly. However, when NNED was retained in the p-NIPAM and the deposited AS first came into contact with the sample, the device did not change its colour depending on the nitrite concentration (Fig. S18).

Therefore, the sample was first deposited onto part 3, and once the sample reached the detection zone (4) where NNED was retained, the heater was activated. Therefore, the AS was released from p-NIPAM (1), arriving at the detection zone (4) and taking place the reaction, changing the colour according to the nitrite concentration in the sample. To control the flow and avoid the sample to move onto the p-NIPAM channel instead of heading to the detection channel, p-NIPAM ionogel was included (2) and the angle between the channels was studied. Finally, 30 s after the collapse of p-NIPAM, a picture was taken of the detection zone and the colour change analysed.

The influence of the angle between channels A and B was studied to avoid that a fraction of reagent contained in p-NIPAM flows through the sample channel instead of the sensing area. To do so, paper devices of the same dimensions were cut with the second channel in angles of 30, 45, 60 and 90 degrees with respect to the first channel. The advance of the flow was measured by counting the time required for a solution to

Fig. 3. Devices with different ionogels volumes before (A) and after (B) Bright Blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. A) Scheme of the μ PAD. B) Photograph of the μ PAD developed.

reach the end of the second channel from the first one (Table SI3).

The results showed that the best angle for the device was 45° , as it was the angle in which a longer time was required for the solution to reach the channel B end, and this minimizes the backflow. The second step in the design of the μ PAD was to optimise the length and width of the channels. To do so, channel A was fixed at a width of 2 mm and different widths of channel B were tested. As previously done, the time to reach the other channel end was measured (Table SI4). The best result was also achieved for the 2 mm width, as it exhibited longer times to reach the end of the channel in which it should not flow.

3.3.1. Structural analysis

ATR-FT-IR analysis was conducted for the structural characterization of the starting materials and the polymer, in order to confirm the successful swelling of AS at 25°C . The vibrational spectrum of the p-NIPAM deswelled was explained in section 3.1.1. The vibrational spectrum of AS reveals characteristic bands of 1042 and 840 cm^{-1} (Table SI1) [38]. The vibrational spectrum of the p-NIPAM swelled with AS reveals the same bands, adding a bands of 3290, 1628, 1540, 1385 and 1178 cm^{-1} , due to the p-NIPAM functional groups (Fig. 2B) [36].

3.3.2. Analytical characterization

Once optimised the μ PAD, calibration from 10^{-7} to 10^{-2} M nitrite concentration was carried out. For this purpose, three replicates were used for each point, being the devices single-used. The curves obtained in the μ PADs were adjusted to an exponential function according to the Eq. 2:

$$y = y_0 + A \cdot \exp(R_0 \cdot x) \quad (2)$$

Once the calibration was obtained (Fig. 5), the LOD and LOQ were calculated, as well as the precision at low (10^{-6} M), middle (10^{-4} M), and high (10^{-2} M) nitrite concentrations ($n = 9$) (Table 2).

The LOD found was 1.7×10^{-7} M and the LOQ 9.3×10^{-7} M. These values were lower than the value established by the World Health Organization [39] as the maximum contaminant level of nitrite ions, (6.5×10^{-6} M). Furthermore, the accuracy proved to be very good, with a CV of less than 2.1% at low concentrations, and around 1% at medium and high concentrations.

4. Conclusions

A μ PAD including stimuli-responsive materials, (p-NIPAM) have been successfully integrated for the determination of nitrites as a proof of concept, showing the feasibility of using them for any type of application that require this kind of approaches.

In this paper, we documented how p-NIPAM repositories can be swelled with the desired reagent and released it at a certain time whenever needed just by heating it. How ionogels can be used to control the flow has also been studied.

Initially, the swelling/deswelling behaviour was studied, showing that p-NIPAM always returned to the same dry weight and did not degrade. Kinetics studies demonstrated that 90 min was the time for highest absorption. When studying the influence of pH, it was found that p-NIPAM absorbs less solution at higher pH values. The required volume of ionogel was also optimised in order to slow the flow.

Once the stimuli-responsive materials were optimised, they were tested in a real application. For this purpose, a colorimetric μ PAD for the determination of nitrite in water was developed, based on Griess chemistry. The cost of fabrication for each sensor, that is an important factor from the industry point of view, is just 1.5 cent.

The detection was performed using a camera and obtaining the Hue coordinate of the HSV colour space. The colour change could be correlated with the nitrite content in the sample. The LOD and LOQ obtained for the optimised sensor were 1.7×10^{-7} M and 9.3×10^{-7} M, respectively.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maria Angustias Torres-Molina: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Celia E. Ramos-Lorente:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ignacio de Orbe-Payá:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nuria López Ruiz:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software. **Pablo Escobedo:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software. **Alberto J. Palma:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Luis F. Capitán-Vallvey:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Miguel M. Erenas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Isabel M. Pérez de Vargas Sansalvador:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

Fig. 5. Calibration of the μ PAD. The insets show the actual photographs of the sensors after exposure to nitrite standard solutions, ranging from 10^{-7} M (left edge) to 10^{-2} M (right edge). A clear colorimetric transition is observed as concentration increases. Data are presented as the mean of three independent replicates and error bars represent the standard deviation.

Table 2

Exponential equation and analytical parameters for μ PAD.

Exponential equation		Analytical parameters	
Y_0	0.84 ± 0.03	LOD (M)	1.7×10^{-7}
A	-0.01 ± 0.01	LOQ (M)	9.3×10^{-7}
R_0	-0.50 ± 0.10	CV 10^{-6} M	2.1%
R^2	0.98	CV 10^{-4} M	1.2%
		CV 10^{-2} M	0.8%

the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2026.117598>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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